

Chemistry of Leucoanthocyanidins

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The leucoanthocyanidins are colorless, natural phenolic substances, which yield anthocyanidins on treatment with hot concentrated acids. The production of red colours from colourless material present in certain flowers, fruits, and leaves on treatment with strong acid has long been known. Their presence was reported in the leaves of the summer lime¹, in white grapes², and apples³. Robinson and Robinson⁴ after a survey of the distribution of these compounds have shown that leucoanthocyanidins are widely distributed in plant kingdom, particularly in tannin-bearing plants and that majority of them (84%) yield cyanidin, and the rest, with a few exceptions, yield delphinidin. Paper chromatography of some commercial tannin extracts⁵ has shown that a series of leucoanthocyanidins of increasing molecular weight in the range 300-1500 is usually present and that those of lowest molecular weight are most mobile when the chromatogram is developed with 2% acetic acid. These mobile compounds are monomeric leucoanthocyanidins and are identical with hydroxylated flavan-3,4-diols (II); some of them have been isolated in pure form⁶.

In recent years there has been a growing tendency to regard leucoanthocyanidins as the possible precursors of 'Condensed tannins'. They can condense much more rapidly than the catechins. Their dimerization may occur between the 4-hydroxyl of one unit with C(6) or C(8) hydrogen of the other unit. In nature they are probably formed in the leaves and then move with carbohydrates and other materials down into the sapwood and heartwood, where they ultimately change into tannins and phlobaphene in course of time.

Because of their increased importance in the study of natural flavanoids, several methods have been developed in recent years to synthesise flavan-diols, especially flavan-3,4-diols⁷. Some of these methods are stereospecific, whereas others yield a mixture of racemates. Thus King and Clark-Lewis^{6b} synthesised ($\pm$)-7, 8, 3',4'-tetramethoxyflavan-3,4-diol (II: R'⁶=H, R=R'=R''=R'''=OMe) (2e, 3a, 4e') by the catalytic hydrogenation of the corresponding flavonol (I: R'=R''=R'''=OMe). Hydrogenation of dihydroflavonol (III) has given varied results. Kulkarni and Joshi^{7a} have reported the formation of a *cis*-4'-methoxy-6-methylflavan-3,4-diol (2e, 3e, 4a') by the hydrogenation of 4'-methoxy-6-methyldihydroflavonol in acidic medium, though Boggar and Rakosi^{7b} obtained by the hydrogenation of dihydroflavonol in acidic medium a flavan-3,4-diol, which was identical with the flavan-3-, 4-diol that they obtained by metal hydride reduction of dihydroflavonol. The latter diol is a mixture of racemates as has recently been shown by the same authors^{7c}. Reduction of dihydroflavonols by metal hydrides generally gives a mixture of racemates, some of which have been separated either by their fractional crystallisation^{6d} or by the column chromatography of their acetates^{7a}. A new stereospecific method for the diol synthesis proceeds via the 4-amino compound of the dihydroflavonol, which has been shown to yield exclusively the 4- α -epimer^{7c}. Another stereospecific synthesis consists in the introduction of an acetoxy group of the C(4) of a 3-hydroxyflavan by lead tetra-acetate followed by hydrolysis⁸. The yield in the last method, however, drops considerably as the flavan nuclei are increasingly substituted by the methoxyl groups. The causes for side-reactions in these cases have been explored by these authors and they have established that in a highly methoxylated flavanoid molecule C(2) and the highly anionoid

group. Baur, Birch, and Hillis⁶ pointed out that the first stage of transformation of a leucoanthocyanidin to anthocyanidin was the formation of a 3-ketoflavan by acid-catalysed dehydration. Flavan-3-ones like flavan-3, 4-diols are in the same state of oxidation as dihydroanthocyanidins so that flavylum salts must be produced by oxidation. Overall mechanistic possibilities are direct oxidation and disproportionation. The low yield of anthocyanidins from leucoanthocyanidins is due to a competing reaction leading to condensed tannins. This is explicable if flavan-3-ones are intermediates, for they would be very unstable and their polymerization could occur by aldol type of condensations of the ketone group with the phloroglucinol nucleus⁹⁻²⁰.

Bokadia, Brown, and Cummings⁶ have investigated in detail the cleavage of flavan-3,4-diols by lead tetra-acetate. This fission product in the case of simple flavan-3, 4-diol (II:R=R'=R''=R'''=R''''=H) was proved to be 2-phenyl-2-formyl-3-hydroxy-2,3-dihydrobenzofuran (V). Treatment of this dihydrobenzofuran with dilute sulphuric acid or its sublimation afforded 2-phenylbenzofuran²¹ (VI). The entire sequence could be represented as follows:

In the acidic medium the dialdehyde (IV), the initial cleavage product, undergoes an acid-catalysed intramolecular aldol-condensation to form the hydroxyaldehyde (V), which changes into 2-phenylbenzofuran by the following ionic mechanism:

The steric squeezing out effect of the bulky phenyl group may also help the elimination at C(2). In case of pyrolysis the conversion may involve a cyclic transition state (VII).

The above conversion is significant in view of the recent findings of Gramshaw *et al.*²², who have shown that flavan-2,3-diols may also be regarded as another type of leucoanthocyanidins, since these also yield anthocyanidins on treatment with acid. Thus 3', 4', 5, 7-tetramethoxyflavan-2,3-diol (VIII), which mostly exists as dihydro- α -2-dihydroxy-4,6,3',4'-tetramethoxychalkone (IX), yields cyanidin chloride tetramethyl ether (X) on treatment with acid. These findings also validate the original formulation of Robinson

and Robinson⁴ of leucoanthocyanidins as flavan-2, 3, 4-triols (XI). Hence a method to differentiate among flavan-2, 3-diols, flavan-3, 4-diols, and flavan-2, 3, 4-triols would be

of great practical importance in the study of leucoanthocyanidins. The periodate fission of 3',4',5,7-tetramethoxyflavan-2,3-diol afforded a mixture of veratric acid and an aldehyde-ester (XII). Although the ester might be capable of intramolecular condensation, this has not been reported²². Even if condensation occurred, the resulting dihydrobenzofuran (XIII) would be expected to undergo dehydration to form 2-aryl-3-formylbenzofuran (XIV) rather than elimination of formic acid to form 2-arylbenzofuran (XV)

A flavan-2, 3, 4-triol (XI) would yield on oxidation an aldehyde-ester (XVI) which is incapable of any intramolecular condensation. From the evidence cited above it follows that the conversion of a flavan-3, 4-diol into a 2-arylbenzofuran can be used to differentiate it from 2, 3-diols and 2,3,4-triols.

To test the general applicability of the method, it was applied to 4'-methoxyflavan-3,4-diol. The conversion occurred in a very good overall yield to furnish 2-*p*-methoxyphenyl-

benzofuran (XVII: R=H, R'=OMe). When this method was applied to 3', 4', 5, 7-tetra-methoxyflavan-3,4-diol, the results were, however, rather disappointing with acetic acid as a solvent. Replacement of acetic acid by benzene yielded a product, which on acid treatment afforded a 5% yield of 4, 6-dimethoxy-2-(3', 4'-dimethoxyphenyl)-benzofuran (XVII: R=R'=OMe).

This conversion can also be used in finding the positions of the hydroxyl groups in the two benzene nuclei provided that the corresponding reference compounds, viz. 2-arylbenzofurans, are known and it provides a new method for flavanoid ring contraction.

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